

Imperial College
London

Submitted for the MSc in Ecology, Evolution and Conservation

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Submission date: 2021/8/26

SUPPORTING INFORMATION FOR

A meta-analysis of reforestation and natural forests on topsoil properties at the global scale

Table S1 Raw data used in this study.

Reference	location	Sample time	MAT	MAP	Coordinate	Altitude (m.a.s.l)	Forest management	Vegetation	Soil Type	Depth cm
			Unit: °C	Unit: mm						
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Bad Helmstedt	May and July 2014	9.4	608	52°13'94" N 11°3'12" E	165	Natural forest Over 100 years	Fagus sylvatica, Larix decidua	Stagnic Cambisol	0-10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Bad Helmstedt	May and July 2014	9.4	608	52°13'94" N 11°3'12" E	165	reforestation 65 years	Fagus sylvatica, Larix decidua	Stagnic Cambisol	0-10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Hohnstedt	May and July 2014	9.7	685	52°22'45" N 10°42'51" E	110	Natural forest Over 236	Fagus sylvatica, Quercus robur	Stagnic Cambisol	0-10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Hohnstedt	May and July 2014	9.7	685	52°22'45" N 10°42'51" E	110	Reforestation 143 years	Fagus sylvatica, Quercus robur	Stagnic Cambisol	0+10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Kreuzheide	May and July 2014	9.7	635	52°27'32" N 10°46'54" E	75	Natural forest Over 115 years	Pinus sylvestris	Dystric Cambisol	0+10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Kreuzheide	May and July 2014	9.7	635	52°27'32" N 10°46'54" E	75	Reforestation 63 years	Quercus petraea	Dystric Cambisol	0+10

(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Reinhausen	May and July 2014	8.1	747	51°26'22" N 10°0'19" E	345	Natural forest Over 142 years	Quercus robur	Stagnic Luvisol	0-10
(Alcantara et al., 2017)	Reinhausen	May and July 2014	8.1	747	51°26'22" N 10°0'19" E	345	Reforestation 73 years	Quercus robur and Fagus sylvatica	Stagnic Luvisol	0-10
(Antisari et al., 2015)	Northern Emilia-Tuscany Apennines, Italy	2014	9	1270	44°11'25"N 10°38'37"E	1010	Natural beech forests Over 100 years	F. sylvatica, L. with Picea abies L., Picea alba Mill., Pseudotsuga menziesii Franco, Pinus mugo Turra and Pinus nigra Arnold	Epileptic Cambisols	0-5
(Antisari et al., 2015)	Northern Emilia-Tuscany Apennines, Italy	2014	9	1270	44°11'25"N 10°38'37"E	1028	Douglas-fir reforestations 70 years	(P. menziesii Franco)	Epileptic Cambisols	0-5
(Antisari et al., 2015)	Northern Emilia-Tuscany Apennines, Italy	2014	9	2100	44°11'25"N 10°38'37"E	1284	Natural beech forests Over 100 years	F. sylvatica, L. with Picea abies L., Picea alba Mill., Pseudotsuga menziesii Franco, Pinus mugo Turra and Pinus nigra Arnold	Epileptic Cambisols	0-5
(Antisari et al., 2015)	Northern Emilia-Tuscany Apennines, Italy	2014	9	2100	44°11'25"N 10°38'37"E	1281	Douglas-fir reforestations 70 years	(P. menziesii Franco)	Epileptic Cambisols	0-5
(Bini et al., 2013)	Guarapuava, Paraná State	November 2007	20	1400-1600	25°23'15"S 51°25'09"W	1120	Native forest	Allophylus edulis, Araucaria angustifolia, Campomanesia xanthocarpa, Capsicodendron dinisii, Casearia decandra, Dicksonia sellowiana, Ilex paraguariensis, Ocotea pulchella, Pimenta pseudocaryophyllus, Vitex megapotamica, Zanthoxylum rhoifolium	Typic Acrudox	0-10
(Bini et al., 2013)	Guarapuava, Paraná State	November 2007	20	1400-1600	25°23'15"S 51°25'09"W	1120	Reforestation with Araucaria angustifolia 32 years	Araucaria angustifolia; understory with Capsicodendron dinisii, Fleurya aestuans, Geophila sp., Pteridium sp., Solanum paniculatum, Solanum pseudocapsicum	Typic Acrudox	0-10

(Bini et al., 2013)	Guarapuava, Paraná State	November 2007	20	1400-1600	25°23'15"S 51°25'09"W	1120	Secondary forest	Acacia plumosa, Mimosa scabrella, Nectandra megapotamica, Ocotea sp, Piper mikanianum, Pteridium sp, Solanum verbascifolium	Typic Acrudox	0-10
							13 years			
(Bini et al., 2013)	Guarapuava, Paraná State	November 2007	20	1400-1600	25°23'15"S 51°25'09"W	1120	Reforestation	Pinus elliottii	Typic Acrudox	0-10
							21 years			
(Bonner et al., 2019)	Leyte Island in the Philippines	April 2015	26 -29	4000	9°55'-10°48' N 124°17'-125°18' E	NA	Mahogany plantation	<i>Swietenia macrophylla</i> King (Meliaceae)	Typic Eutrudepts	0-10
							20 years			
(Bonner et al., 2019)	Leyte Island in the Philippines	April 2015	26 -29	4000	9°55'-10°48' N 124°17'-125°18' E	NA	Mixed plantation	Dipterocarpaceae trees and other 100 species (Nguyen et al., 2014)	Typic Eutrudepts	0-10
							18 years			
(Bonner et al., 2019)	Leyte Island in the Philippines	April 2015	26 -29	4000	9°55'-10°48' N 124°17'-125°18' E	NA	Selectively logged rainforest	<i>Some native species (Nguyen et al., 2014)</i>	Typic Eutrudepts	0-10
							Over 30 years			
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tanakeke Island, Indonesia	2017	27.5	3086	5°27'32"S 119°18'01"E	NA	Mature forest	Rhizophora apiculate and Rhizophora stylosa	NA	0-25
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tanakeke Island, Indonesia	2017	27.5	3086	5°27'32"S 119°18'01"E	NA	Rehabilitated mangroves	Rhizophora stylosa and Ceriops tagal	NA	0-25
							10 years			
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tiwoho, North Sulawesi	2017	26	5310	1°34'44"N 124°49'07"E	NA	Mature forest	Rhizophora apiculate and Rhizophora stylosa	NA	0-25
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tiwoho, North Sulawesi	2017	26	5310	1°34'44"N 124°49'07"E	NA	Rehabilitated mangroves	Ceriops tagal and Rhizophora apiculate	NA	0-25
							10 years			
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tiwoho, North Sulawesi	2017	26	5310	1°34'44"N 124°49'07"E	NA	Rehabilitated mangroves	Ceriops tagal and Rhizophora apiculate	NA	0-25
							10 years			

(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tiwoho, North Sulawesi	2017	26	5310	1°34'44"N 124°49'07"E	NA	Mature forest	Ceriops tagal and Rhizophora apiculata	NA	0-25
(Cameron et al., 2019)	Tiwoho, North Sulawesi	2017	26	5310	1°34'44"N 124°49'07"E	NA	Rehabilitated mangroves 10 years	Ceriops tagal, Sonneratia alba and Rhizophora apiculata	NA	0-25
(Chang et al., 2017)	North-central part of Taiwan	2016	12	4000	24° 35'N, 121°24' E	1700 - 2220	Natural <i>Chamaecyparis</i> forest over 100	Hinoki cypress (<i>Chamaecyparis obtusa</i> Sieb. & Zucc. var. <i>formosana</i> (Hayata) Rehder(<i>C. formosensis</i> Matsum.	NA	0-10
(Chang et al., 2017)	North-central part of Taiwan	2016	12	4000	24° 35'N, 121°24' E	1700 - 2220	Disturbed forest. 15 years	<i>Chamaecyparis</i>	NA	0-10
(Chang et al., 2017)	North-central part of Taiwan	2016	12	4000	24° 35'N, 121°24' E	1700 - 2220	Second disturbed forest 50 years	<i>Chamaecyparis</i>	NA	0-10
(Chang et al., 2017)	North-central part of Taiwan	2016	12	4000	24° 35'N, 121°24' E	1700 - 2220	Secondary Japanese 30 years	Japanese cedar- <i>Cryptomeria japonica</i>	NA	0-10
(Chernov et al., 2021)	Cat Tien (Dong Nai) National Park	November 2018	25.4	2450	11°24'29" N 107°23'04" E	130-150	Natural forest without clear cutting over 80 years	<i>Dipterocarpus alatus</i> , <i>Fabaceae</i> , <i>Euphorbiaceae</i> , <i>Clusiaceae</i> , <i>Myrtaceae</i> and <i>Verbenaceae</i> families	Fluvisols IUSS 2014	0-10
(Chernov et al., 2021)	Cat Tien (Dong Nai) National Park	November 2018	25.4	2450	11°23'58" N 107°22'25" E	130-150	Trees plantation 20 years	<i>Dipterocarpus alatus</i> , <i>Anisoptera costata</i> , <i>Hopea odorata</i> , <i>Lagerstroemia calyculata</i> , <i>Sindora cochinchinensis</i> , <i>Xylia</i> <i>xylocarpa</i> , <i>Cassia fistula</i> , <i>Cassia siamea</i> , <i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i> , <i>Mimusops elengis</i> , <i>Ochna integerrima</i> , <i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i> .	Fluvisols	0-10
(Chernov et al., 2021)	Cat Tien (Dong Nai) National Park	November 2018	25.4	2450	11°23'49" N 107°22'28" E	130-150	Trees plantation 32 years	Forest plantation with domination of <i>Dipterocarpus</i> (mostly <i>Dipterocarpus alatus</i>)	Fluvisols	0-10
(Chia et al., 2020)	Gyeonggi-do, South Korea	2018	11.7C	1300	127° 10' 51"E, 37° 45' 56"N	227	Deciduous Natural Forest 106 years	<i>Quercus serrata</i> , <i>Acer pseudosieboldianum</i> , <i>Sorbus alnifolia</i> and <i>Q.</i> <i>variabilis</i> .	brown forest soils	0-10

(Chia et al., 2020)	Gyeonggi-do, South Korea	2018	11.7C	1300	127° 10' 57"E, 37° 45' 55"N	202	Coniferous plantation 70 years	<i>P. koraiensis</i>	brown forest soils	0-10
(Chia et al., 2020)	Gyeonggi-do, South Korea	2018	11.7C	1300	127° 10' 55"E 37° 46' 37" N	220	Coniferous and deciduous forest 50 years	<i>P. koraiensis</i> <i>Q. serrata</i>	brown forest soils	0-10
(Chia et al., 2020)	Gyeonggi-do, South Korea	2018	11.7C	1300	127° 10' 54"E 37° 45' 23" N	113	Coniferous plantation 7 years	<i>P. koraiensis</i>	brown forest soils	0-10
(Deng et al., 2018)	Eastern Liaoning Province, China	July 2017	6.4	1,158	40° 50' 00"- 40° 57' 12"N 124° 44' 07' -124° 57'30"E	525.6	Natural secondary forest Over 100 years	<i>Hemiptelea davidii</i> , <i>Leymus chinensis</i>	NA	0-10
(Deng et al., 2018)	Eastern Liaoning Province, China	July 2017	6.4	1,158	40° 50' 00"- 40° 57' 12"N 124° 44' 07' -124° 57'30"E	552.7	Plantation forest 40 years	<i>Daemonorops margaritae</i>	NA	0-10
(Deng et al., 2018)	Eastern Liaoning Province, China	July 2017	6.4	1,158	40° 50' 00"- 40° 57' 12"N 124° 44' 07' -124° 57'30"E	552.7	Plantation forest 40 years	<i>Daemonorops margaritae</i> , <i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	NA	0-10
(Dymov et al., 2018)	Komi Republic, Russia	2017	10	600	60°21'37"N 49°14'52"E	140–150	Green moss spruce forest	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L., <i>Betula pubescens</i> Ehrh., <i>P. obovata</i> Ledeb. and <i>Populus tremula</i> L.	Retisol	0-8
(Dymov et al., 2018)	Komi Republic, Russia	2017	10	600	60°21'37"N 49°14'52"E	140–150	Reforestation 19 years	<i>Aegopodium podagraria</i> L., <i>Carex praecox</i> Schreb. and <i>Geranium sylvaticum</i> L.	Retisol	0-10
(Dymov et al., 2018)	Komi Republic, Russia	2017	10	600	60°21'37"N 49°14'52"E	140–150	Reforestation 85 years	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i> L., <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i> L. and <i>Asarum europaeum</i> L.	Retisol	0-10
(Fang et al., 2016)	Changbai Mountain area	July 2011	1.2	920	42° 20'–42° 40' N 127° 29'–128° 02' E	600 – 800	Old-growth Forest Over 150 years	Korean pine and native broadleaf tree species including <i>Tilia amurensis</i> Rupr., <i>Quercus mongolica</i> Fisch. ex Ledeb., and <i>Fraxinus mandshurica</i>	Udalfs	0-10
(Fang et al., 2016)	Changbai Mountain area	July 2011	1.2	920	42° 20'–42° 40' N 127° 29'–128° 02' E	600 -800	Birch forest 40 years	<i>B. platyphylla</i> , <i>P. amurense</i> , <i>F. mandshurica</i> , <i>T. amurensis</i>	Udalfs	0-10

(Fang et al., 2016)	Changbai Mountain area	July 2011	1.2	920	42° 20'–42° 40' N 127° 29'–128° 02' E	600 -800	Mixed broadleaf/larch forest 40 years	Phellodendron amurense Rupr., Juglans mandshurica Maxim., Acer pseudo-sieboldianum (Pax) Komarov, and T. amurensis.	Udalfs	0-10
(Fang et al., 2016)	Spruce plantation	July 2011	1.2	920	42° 20'–42° 40' N 127° 29'–128° 02' E	600 -800	Spruce plantation 40 years	Spruce	Udalfs	0-10
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°46'17" S, 152°49'51" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 3 years	Flindersia schottiana, Homolanthus nutans, Ficus coronate, Flindersia bennettiana, Podocarpus elatus and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°46'06" S, 152°50'46" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 4 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°42'01" S, 152°53'58" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 6 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°46'10" S, 152°49'57" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 7 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°44'46" S, 152°51'13" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 8 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°46'12" S, 152°49'39" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 11 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°46'08" S, 152°49'43" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 12 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°42'01" S, 152°51'02" E	196 - 441	Reforestation 20 years	Homolanthus nutans, Podocarpus elatus, Ficus coronate, Flindersia schottiana and Acacia melanoxylon	Nitisol	0-15
(Gageler et al., 2014)	Maleny region in Queensland, Australia	May and June 2013	18.7	1900	26°44'50" S, 152°51'11" E	196 - 441	Remnant Forest	Acacia melanoxylon, Flindersia schottiana and Ficus coronata	Nitisol	0-15
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2011)	Los Pescados, Mexico	May 2006	8.4	1079	19°20'–40'N 97°00'–15'W	3350	Forest over 40 years	P. montezumae, Abies religiosa	Silandic, Umbric Andosol	0-10

(Gamboa & Galicia, 2011)	Los Pescados, Mexico	May 2006	8.4	1079	19°20'–40'N 97°00'–15'W	3350	Regeneration 20 years	Baccharis conferta	Silandic, Umbric Andosol	0-10
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2011)	El Conejo, Mexico	May 2006	7.7	1175	19°20'–40'N 97°00'–15'W	3500	Reference forest 75 years	A. religiosa	Silandic, Umbric Andosol	0-10
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2011)	El Conejo Mexico	May 2006	7.7	1175	19°20'–40'N 97°00'–15'W	3500	Regeneration 12 years	Senecio sp., Lupinus montanus	Silandic, Umbric Andosol	0-10
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	Perote, Mexico	2011	11.7	603	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	2550	Natural forest 30 years	Pinus patula, P. teocote, P. oaxacana	Pyroclastic deposits	0-6
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	Perote Mexico	2011	11.7	603	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	2550	Reforestation 15 years	Pinus patula, P. teocote, P. oaxacana	Pyroclastic deposits	0-4
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	Los Pescados, Mexico	2011	8.4	1079	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3350	Natural forest 40 years	P. montezumae, Abies religiosa	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-5
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	Los Pescados, Mexico	2011	8.4	1079	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3350	Reforestation 20 years	Baccharis conferta	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-6
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	Los Pescados, Mexico	2011	8.4	1079	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3350	Reforestation 20 years	P. montezumae, A. religiosa	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-11
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	El Conejo, Mexico	2011	7.7	1175	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3500	Natural forest 75 years	A. religiosa	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-7
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	El Conejo, Mexico	2011	7.7	1175	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3500	Reforestation 23 years	P. montezumae, A. religiosa	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-6
(Gamboa & Galicia, 2012)	El Conejo Mexico	2011	7.7	1175	19°20'–19°40' N, 97°00'–97°15' W	3500	Reforestation 12 years	Senecio sp., Lupinus montanus	Colluvial and pyroclastic deposits	0-7.5

(Gong et al., 2019)	Ningnan county, Sichuan, China	2018	20	800	27°04'15" N 102°43'42" E	1260	Natural forest About 200 years	L. leucocephala, Eucalyptus camaldulensis, Acacia confusa, Bombax ceiba, Melia azedarach, Tamarindus indica, and Trema tomentosa	Chromic Cambisol	0-20
(Gong et al., 2019)	Ningnan county, Sichuan, China	2018	20	800	27°04'15" N 102°43'42" E	1273	Mixed plantation 26 years	L. leucocephala and C. cajan	Chromic Cambisol	0-20
(Guo et al., 2016)	Castanopsis kawakamii Nature Reserve	April 2011	19.1	1749	26° 11' N, 117° 28' E	180-604	old-growth evergreen, broadleaved forest 200 years	Castanopsis kawakamii, Schima superba, Litsea subcoriacea, Elaeocarpus decipiens and Castanopsis carlesii	oxisol	0-10
(Guo et al., 2016)	Chenda Experimental Station	April 2011	19.1	1749	26° 19' N, 117° 36' E	180-604	Chinese fir 36 years	Cunninghamia lanceolata (Chinese fir) and P. massoniana	oxisol	0-10
(Guo et al., 2016)	Chenda Experimental Station	April 2011	19.1	1749	26° 19' N, 117° 36' E	180-604	Pinus massoniana 36 years	Cunninghamia lanceolata (Chinese fir) and P. massoniana	oxisol	0-10
(Ha ad et al., 2020)	South Punjab Pakistan	2015	13.8	255	30°32'17"N 72°40'18"E	164.54	Forestland 87 years	Eucalyptus (<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>), mulberry (<i>Mores albs</i>), simal (<i>Bombaxceiba</i>), kikar (<i>Vachillianilolica</i>), bakain (<i>Meliaazadirachta</i>), and bamboo (<i>Bambusoideae</i>) trees	NA	0-20
(Ha ad et al., 2020)	South Punjab Pakistan	2015	13.8	255	30°15'39"N 72°68'83"E	148.35	Agroforest land 25-30 years	Eucalyptus (<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i>) and simal (<i>Bom- baxceiba</i>)	NA	0-20
(Hiltbrunner et al., 2013)	Canton of Fribourg, Switzerland	2011	11.4	1250	7°50'54"E 46°37'17"N	1520	Forest 30 years	Norway spruce (<i>Picea abies</i> L.)	NA	0-10
(Hiltbrunner et al., 2013)	Canton of Fribourg, Switzerland	2011	11.4	1,250	7°50'54"E 46°37'17"N	1520	Forest 40 years	Norway spruce (<i>Picea abies</i> L.)	NA	0-10
(Hiltbrunner et al., 2013)	Canton of Fribourg, Switzerland	2011	11.4	1,250	7°50'54"E 46°37'17"N	1450	Forest 45 years	Norway spruce (<i>Picea abies</i> L.)	NA	0-10

(Hiltbrunner et al., 2013)	Canton of Fribourg, Switzerland	2011	11.4	1,250	7°50'54"E 46°37'17"N	1450	Old-growth Forest 120 years	Norway spruce (<i>Picea abies</i> L.)	NA	0-10
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	July 2012	25.9 °C	4752	8°41'N, 83°13'W	210	Natural forest Over 100 years	<i>Iriartea deltoidei</i> , <i>Welfia regia</i> , <i>Compsonura excelsa</i> , <i>Socratea exorrhiza</i> , <i>Perebea hispidula</i> , <i>Qualea paracensis</i> , <i>Carapa nicaraguensis</i> and <i>Symphonia globulifera</i>	Ultisol	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	162	Forest plots 10 years	<i>Vochysia ferruginea</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	166	Forest plots 13 years	<i>V. ferruginea</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	151	Forest plots 25 years	<i>Gmelina arborea</i> , <i>V. ferruginea</i> , <i>M. affinis</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	119	Forest plots 27.5 years	<i>V. ferruginea</i> , <i>Psychotria elata</i> , <i>Siparuna andina</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	113	Forest plots 35 years	<i>G. chiriquiensis</i> , <i>Apeiba membranacea</i> , <i>Tetrathylacium macrophyllum</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Hofhansl et al., 2020; Oberleitner et al., 2021)	southwestern Costa Rica	2015	28.2	5910	8°42'03" N, 83°12'06" W	123	Forest plots 40 years	<i>V. ferruginea</i> , <i>T. macrophyllum</i> , <i>G. amplifolia</i>	Ultisols and Inceptisols	0-15
(Jin et al., 2019)	Jiuling Mountain Guanshan National Nature Reserve	August 2016	16.2	1700	28°30'–28°40'N 114°29'–114°45'E	200 -1480	Native evergreen broad- leaved forest	<i>Castanopsis tibetana</i> <i>Alniphyllum fortune</i> <i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i> <i>Itea oblonga</i> <i>Bothrocaryum controversum</i> <i>Tapiscia sinensis</i> <i>Viscum coloratum</i>	Haplic Aliso FAO	0-15
(Jin et al., 2019)	Jiuling Mountain Guanshan National Nature Reserve	August 2016	16.2	1700	28°30'–28°40'N 114°29'–114°45'E	200-1480 30 years	coniferous forest	<i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i> <i>Alniphyllum fortune</i> <i>Itea oblonga</i> <i>Eurya japonica</i> <i>Photinia davidsoniae</i> <i>Camellia caudata</i> <i>Ligustrum quihoui</i>	Haplic Aliso FAO	0-15

(Jin et al., 2019)	Jiuling Mountain	August 2016	16.2	1700	28°30'–28°40'N		broad-leaved conifer	Cunninghamia lanceolata <i>Carpinus turczaninowii</i> Alniphyllum		0-15
	Guanshan National					200 - 1480	mixed forest	fortune Michelia skinneriana Itea oblonga Schima superba	Haplic Aliso FAO	
	Nature Reserve				114°29'–114°45'E		25 years	<i>Castanopsis eyrei</i> <i>Elaeocarpus japonicus</i>		
(Jin et al., 2019)	Jiuling Mountain	August 2016	16.2	1700	28°30'–28°40'N		broad-leaved conifer	Rhododendron latoucheae <i>Stewartia sinensis</i> Cyclobalanopsis		0-15
	Guanshan National					200 - 1480	mixed forest	myrsinifolia <i>Alniphyllum fortune</i> <i>Carpinus viminea</i> <i>Lindera</i>	Haplic Aliso FAO	
	Nature Reserve				114°29'–114°45'E		10 years	<i>erythrocarpa</i> <i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i> <i>Toxicodendron vernicifluum</i>		
(Jin et al., 2019)	Jiuling Mountain	August 2016	16.2	1700	28°30'–28°40'N		broad-leaved conifer	Dichroa febrifuga <i>Bothrocaryum controversum</i> <i>Alniphyllum fortune</i>		0-15
	Guanshan National					200-1480	mixed forest	<i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i> <i>Toona ciliata</i> <i>MaChilus leptophylla</i> <i>Acer</i>	Haplic Aliso FAO	
	Nature Reserve				114°29'–114°45'E		5 years	<i>dauidii</i> <i>Camellia oleifera</i> <i>Evodia fargesii</i>		
(Jourgholami et al., 2019)	Tyrumrud region of	June 2017	13.8	1090	36° 48' 21"- 36° 48' 37"N	420	Natural mixed forest	Hombeam (<i>Carpinus betulus</i>) – Oak (<i>Quercus castaneifolia</i>)	Alfisols	0-10
	the Hyrcanian forests				50° 44' 18"- 50° 44' 27" E					
	in Iran									
(Jourgholami et al., 2019)	Tyrumrud region of	June 2017	13.8	1090	36° 48' 21"- 36° 48' 37"N	452	monoculture plantation	Caucasian alder (<i>Alnus subcordata</i>)	Alfisols	0-10
	the Hyrcanian forests				50° 44' 18"- 50° 44' 27" E					
	in Iran						25 years			
(Jourgholami et al., 2019)	Tyrumrud region of	June 2017	13.8	1090	36° 48' 21"- 36° 48' 37"N	461	monoculture plantation	Velvet maple (<i>Acer velutinum</i>)	Alfisols	0-10
	the Hyrcanian forests				50° 44' 18"- 50° 44' 27" E					
	in Iran						25 years			
(Jourgholami et al., 2019)	Tyrumrud region of	June 2017	13.8	1090	36° 48' 21"- 36° 48' 37"N	436	monoculture plantation	Velvet maple (<i>Acer velutinum</i>)	Alfisols	0-10
	the Hyrcanian forests				50° 44' 18"- 50° 44' 27" E					
	in Iran						25 years			

(Kim et al., 2021)	Tva rälund, Sidensjö- Stugun Kulba öksliden	September 2018	10-14	450-900	65°00'28.1"N 19°39'17.9"E	170 -345	Unmanaged forest 80-150 years	lingonberry (<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>) and bilberry (<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>)	podzols	0-10
(Kim et al., 2021)	Tva rälund, Sidensjö- Stugun Kulba öksliden	September 2018	10-14	450-900	65°00'28.1"N 19°39'17.9"E	170 -345	Continuous-cover forestry 5 years	Norway spruce <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> (Scots Pine)	podzols	0-10
(Kim et al., 2021)	Tva rälund, Sidensjö- Stugun Kulba öksliden	September 2018	10-14	450-900	65°00'28.1"N 19°39'17.9"E	170 -345	Clear-fell forestry 4 years	Norway spruce <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> (Scots Pine)	podzols	0-10
(Kononen et al., 2018)	Kalimantan, Indonesia	September 2014	26.2	2540	2°19'16" S 113° 53'43" E	NA	Swamp forest Over 20 years	Near-pristine peat swamp forest	NA	0-5
(Kononen et al., 2018)	Kalimantan, Indonesia	September 2014	26.2	2540	2°18'54. "S, 114° 03'31" E	NA	Reforested site 6 years	Shorea balangeran trees	NA	0-5
(Kooch et al., 2020)	Galandrood district in northern Iran	August 2017	15	1300	36°30'40"-36° 37'30"N 51°28'25"-51° 26'30"E	100	Natural forest Over 40 years	<i>Carpinus betulus</i> <i>Parrotia persica</i> <i>Brachypodium pinnatum</i> <i>Carex sylvatica</i> <i>Coryza bonariensis</i> <i>Cyclamen coum</i> <i>Calystegia sepium</i> <i>Oxalis corniculata</i> <i>Oplismenus undulatifolius</i> <i>Primula heterochroma</i> <i>Parietaria officinalis</i>	Alfisols	0-10
(Kooch et al., 2020)	Galandrood district in northern Iran	August 2017	15	1300	36°30'40"-36° 37'30"N 51° 28' 25"-51° 26' 30"E	100 m	Oak plantation 32 years	<i>Quercus castaneifolia</i>	Alfisols	0-10
(Krainovic et al., 2020)	Maués, Amazonas State, Brazil	2018	27.2	1997	3°32'44"S, 57°41'30"W	NA	Rosewood plantations 4 years	Aniba rosaeodora Ducke	Red-Yellow Latosol	0-10
(Krainovic et al., 2020)	Maués, Amazonas State, Brazil	2018	27.2	1997	3°32'44"S, 57°41'30"W	NA	Rosewood plantations 10 years	Aniba rosaeodora Ducke	Red-Yellow Latosol	0-10
(Krainovic et al., 2020)	Maués, Amazonas State, Brazil	2018	27.2	1997	3°32'44"S, 57°41'30"W	NA	Rosewood plantations 20 years	Aniba rosaeodora Ducke	Red-Yellow Latosol	0-10

(Krainovic et al., 2020)	Maués, Amazonas State, Brazil	2018	27.2	1997	3°32'44"S, 57°41'30"W	NA	Native forest Over 60 years	Paullinia cupana Kunth, Sapindaceae	Red-Yellow Latosol	0-10
(Kumar et al., 2010)	Rajasthan, Western India	2009	NA	610	23°3'-30°12' N 69°30'-78°17E	NA	Deciduous Forests Over 50 years	Acacia niolita L. tree Tectona grandis Linn. Butea monosperma (Lam.) Taub.	alluvial	0-10
(Kumar et al., 2010)	Rajasthan, Western India	2009	NA	610	23°3'-30°12' N 69°30'-78°17E	NA	Plantation 25 years	Acacia leucophloea, Acacia nilotica, Tectona grandis Linn., Wrightia tinctoria and Butea monosperma	Alluvial	0-10
(Kurganova et al., 2018)	Kostroma oblast, European Russia	2015	4.3 °C	601	58°10' N 44°28' E	NA	Secondary birch- spruce forest About 100 years	Birch spruce forest	Soddy-podzolic	0-10
(Kurganova et al., 2018)	Kostroma oblast, European Russia	2015	4.3 °C	601	58°10' N, 44°28' E	NA	Aspen-birch forest 35 years	Birch spruce forest	Soddy-podzolic	0-10
(Kurganova et al., 2018)	Belgorod oblast, Borisovka raion	2015	6.0 °C	565	50°36' N, 36°01' E	NA	Plantations 35-40 years	wild pear, birch, ash-tree, oak, and linden	Dark gray forest loamy	0-10
(Kurganova et al., 2018)	Belgorod oblast, Borisovka raion	2015	6.0 °C	565	50°36' N, 36°01' E	NA	Native forest About 150 years old	native maple and oak forest	Dark gray forest loamy	0-10
(Kurganova et al., 2021)	Manturovo district, Kostroma oblast, Russia	2019	3.6	644	58°10'54.0" N 44°28'21.6" E	NA	Myrtillus aspen-birch forest 45 years	Myrtillus aspen-birch forest	Albic Retisols	0-5
(Kurganova et al., 2021)	Manturovo district, Kostroma oblast, Russia	2019	3.6	644	58°10'56.1" N 44°28'29.0" E	NA	Myrtillus-moss spruce-birch forest 120 years	Myrtillus-moss spruce-birch forest	Albic Retisols	0-5
(Lan et al., 2017)	Xishuangbanna National Nature Reserve	September 2015	21.0	1532	21° 36'N 101° 34'E	580	Rubber plantations 20 years	Cyrtococcum patens, Co elina co unis, and Cyclosorus interruptus.	Latosols	0-20

(Lan et al., 2017)	Xishuangbanna	September 2015	21.0	1532				Secondary tropical forest	Litsea mollis, Litsea umbellate, Litsea elongate, Schefflera		0-20
	National Nature Reserve				21° 36'N 101° 34'E	630			bodinieri, Phoebe lanceolate, Ficus hirta, Goniolalamus griffithii, and Pratia nu ularia	Latosols	
(Lan et al., 2017)	Xishuangbanna	September 2015	21.0	1532				Tropical seasonal rainforest	Mezzettiopsis creaghii, Ardisia neriifolia, Saprosma ternatum,		0-20
	National Nature Reserve				101° 34'E 21° 36'N	750		Over 45 years	Girroniera subaequalis, Aidia pycnantha, Drypetes indica, and Mussaenda pubescens.	Latosols	
(Lewis et al., 2019)	Northern Queensland	February 2013	19.7 -23.5	1733	17°16'36.1"S 145°37'33.7"E	730		Mixed rainforest species	Eucalyptus umbra, Melaleuca viridiflora	Brown Ferrosol Kandosol	0-10
								8 years			
(Lewis et al., 2019)	Northern Queensland	February 2013	19.7 -23.5	1733	17°16'36.1"S 145°37'33.7"E	730		Remnant rainforest	E. racemosa, E. acmenoides, C. intermedia	Brown Ferrosol Kandosol	0-10
								Over 40 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Cerrato, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	42°07'26"N 4°18'09"W	800 -900		Natural Quercus forest	P. halepensis	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 100 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Cerrato, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	42°07'26"N 4°18'09"W	800 -900		Pinus plantation	Q. ilex subsp ballota	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 40 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Ampudia, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	41°53'04"N 4°45'30"W	800 -900		Natural Quercus forest	P. halepensis	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 100 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Ampudia, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	41°53'04"N 4°45'30"W	800 -900		Pinus plantation	Q. ilex subsp ballota	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 40 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Monte Viejo, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	42°01'02"N 4°32'46"W	800 -900		Natural Quercus forest	P. halepensis	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 100 years			
(Llorente et al., 2010)	Monte Viejo, northwestern Spain	2009	12.3	400	42°01'02"N 4°32'46"W	800 -900		Pinus plantation	Q. ilex subsp ballota	Xerepts	0-10
								Over 40 years			
(Lorenzetti et al., 2019)	Monte Morello, Italy	April 2016	13.9	1,003	43°51'20"N, 11°14'23"E	590 - 650		Reforestation	black pine (Pinus nigra J.F.Arnold), Brutia pine (Pinus brutia Ten. subsp. brutia), and cypress (Cupressus spp.)	Calcaric Cambisols	0-11
								Over 36 years			

(Lorenzetti et al., 2019)	Monte Morello, Italy	April 2016	13.9	1,003	43°51'20"N, 11°14'23"E	590 - 650	Mixed forest Over 107 years	Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.), Downey oak (<i>Quercus pubescens</i> L.) and Flowering ash (<i>Fraxinus ornus</i> L.)	Calcaric Cambisols	0-10
(Lozano-Garcia et al., 2016)	Andalucia-southern Spain	2015	NA	800	38°20'-38°27' N 3°27'-3°37' W	540	Reforested areas 65 years	Pinus pinea and pinaster combined with native species such as holm, Portuguese, and cork oaks (<i>Quercus ilex</i> , <i>Quercus faginea</i> , and <i>Quercus suber</i> , respectively) and laudanum (<i>Cistus ladanifer</i>)	Cambisols, Phaeozems, Leptosols and Regosols	0-25
(Lozano-Garcia et al., 2016)	Andalucia-southern Spain	2015	NA	800	38°20'-38°27' N 3°27'-3°37' W	540	Native forests Over 200 years	oaks (<i>Quercus</i> sp.) while scrublands are dominated by species such as kermes oak (<i>Quercus coccifera</i>), strawberry tree (<i>Arbutus unedo</i>), mastic (<i>Pistacia lentiscus</i>), myrtle (<i>Myrtus co unis</i>), narrow-leaved mock privet (<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i>) and laudanum	Cambisols, Phaeozems, Leptosols and Regosols	0-25
(Lyu et al., 2018)	Sanming city	March 2015	18.7	2025	26°09'24" N, 117°28'03" E	300	mature natural forest	Castanopsis, kawakamii Hayata (Fagaceae)	Oxisol USDA	0-10
(Lyu et al., 2018)	Sanming city	March 2015	18.7	2025	26°09'24" N, 117°28'03" E	300	Chinese fir plantation 42 years	Fir plantation	Oxisol USDA	0-10
(Mackay et al., 2016)	Goulburn Broken catchment	May 2013	16.5	668	39°92' S, 145°98' E	NA	Mixed-species plantings 9 years	Eucalyptus species with grassy understoreys	NA	0-5
(Mackay et al., 2016)	Goulburn Broken catchment	May 2013	16.5	668	39°92' S, 145°98' E	NA	Mixed-species plantings 10years	Eucalyptus species with grassy understoreys	NA	0-5
(Mackay et al., 2016)	Goulburn Broken catchment	May 2013	16.5	668	39°92' S, 145°98' E	NA	Mixed-species plantings 14years	Eucalyptus species with grassy understoreys	NA	0-5
(Mackay et al., 2016)	Goulburn Broken catchment	May 2013	16.5	668	39°92' S, 145°98' E	NA	Mixed-species plantings 23 years	Eucalyptus species with grassy understoreys	NA	0-5
(Mackay et al., 2016)	Goulburn Broken catchment	May 2013	16.5	668	39°92' S, 145°98' E	NA	Natural forest Over 100 years	Eucalyptus camaldulensis	NA	0-5

(Maslov & Maslova, 2020)	Moscow Region, Russia	May to November 2018	3.3	NA	56°23' N, 37°26' E	NA	Near-pristine swamp forest over 70 years	Salix caprea, Betula pendula	NA	0-20
(Maslov & Maslova, 2020)	Moscow Region, Russia	May to November 2018	3.3	NA	56°23' N, 37°26' E	NA	Natural forest vegetation 45-50 years	Betula pendula and Alnus incana	NA	0-20
(McGee et al., 2019)	Maquenque National Wildlife Refuge	July 2014	27	4300	10°40'46.21"N, 84°10'42.10"W	58.8	Primary forest Over 40 years	NA	oxisol	0-15
(McGee et al., 2019)	Maquenque National Wildlife Refuge	July 2014	27	4300	10°41'12.56"N, 84°10'15.65"W	58.9	Old secondary 33 years	NA	oxisol	0-15
(McGee et al., 2019)	Maquenque National Wildlife Refuge	July 2014	27	4300	10°41'12.56"N, 84°10'15.65"W	59.9	young secondary 23 years	NA	oxisol	0-15
(Mujuru et al., 2014)	Mutarazi Estate situated	September 2010	14	1500	19°0'37"S 32°21'29"E	1871	natural forests Moist Forest	Macaranga mellifera, Ilex mitis, Schrebera alata, Rapanea melanophloeos, Olea capensis and Schefflera umbellifera.	Rhodic ferralsols	0-10
(Mujuru et al., 2014)	Mutarazi Estate situated	September 2010	14	1500	19°0'37"S 32°21'29"E	1897	Reforestation 30 years	P. eliottii (Slash Pine), P. taeda (Loblolly Pine), P. patula (Patula Pine), and P. tecunumanii (Tecun Uman Pine). P. patula, Schiede & Deppe	Rhodic ferralsols	0-10
(Mujuru et al., 2014)	Mutarazi Estate situated	September 2010	14	1500	19°0'37"S 32°21'29"E	1875	Reforestation 25 years	P. eliottii (Slash Pine), P. taeda (Loblolly Pine), P. patula (Patula Pine), and P. tecunumanii (Tecun Uman Pine). P. patula, Schiede & Deppe	Rhodic ferralsols	0-10
(Mujuru et al., 2014)	Mutarazi Estate situated	September 2010	14	1500	19°0'37"S 32°21'29"E	1808	Reforestation 20 years	P. eliottii (Slash Pine), P. taeda (Loblolly Pine), P. patula (Patula Pine), and P. tecunumanii (Tecun Uman Pine). P. patula, Schiede & Deppe	Rhodic ferralsols	0-10
(Mujuru et al., 2014)	Mutarazi Estate situated	September 2010	14	1500	19°0'37"S 32°21'29"E	1895	Reforestation 10 years	P. eliottii (Slash Pine), P. taeda (Loblolly Pine), P. patula (Patula Pine), and P. tecunumanii (Tecun Uman Pine). P. patula, Schiede & Deppe	Rhodic ferralsols	0-10

(Nadal-Romero et al., 2016)	Araguás catchment, Central Pyrenees	September 2014	10	800	42°36'16"N 0°37'22"W	920–1105	Natural forest	Genista scorpius, Juniperus co unis, Rosa gr. canina and Buxus sempervirens	Leptic Calcaric Regosols	0-10
(Nadal-Romero et al., 2016)	Araguás catchment, Central Pyrenees	September 2014	10	800	42°36'16"N 0°37'22"W	920–1105	Afforestation 64 years	Pinus nigra	Leptic Calcaric Regosols	0-10
(Nadal-Romero et al., 2016)	Araguás catchment, Central Pyrenees	September 2014	10	800	42°36'16"N 0°37'22"W	920–1105	Afforestation 49 years	Pinus sylvestris	Leptic Calcaric Regosols	0-10
(Pang et al., 2018)	Yunnan Province, southwest China	June 2016	19.8	805	102°54'E, 23°37'N	1.416	Secondary forest	Quercus cocciferoides, Pistacia weinmannifolia	Calcareous soil	0-15
(Pang et al., 2018)	Yunnan Province, southwest China	June 2016	19.8	805	102°54'E, 23°37'N	1.511	EM Plantations 20 years	Eucalyptus maideni	Calcareous soil	0-15
(Pang et al., 2018)	Yunnan Province, southwest China	June 2016	19.8	805	102°54'E, 23°37'N	1.560	PY Plantations 20 years	Pinus yunnanensis	Calcareous soil	0-15
(Pereira et al., 2020)	Bananal	February 2010	24	4320	22°48'26" S 44°21'59" W	985	Native Araucaria Forest Over 120 years	Euterpe edulis, Raulinoreitzi aleptophebia, Cedrela fissilis and Araucaria angustifolia.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol	0-20
(Pereira et al., 2020)	Bananal	February 2010	24	4320	22°48'26" S 44°21'59" W	826	Reforested Araucaria Forest 35 years	Dicksonia sellowiana, Euterpe edulis, Myrcia rostrata, Araucaria angustifolia and shrub, herb and grass species in places with more open vegetation.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol	0-20
(Pereira et al., 2020)	Itaberá	February 2010	24	4320	22°48'26" S 44°21'59" W	678	Native Araucaria Forest preserved native area	Eugenia ligustrina and Soroccea bonplandii, Syagrus romanzoffiana, Matayba elaeagnoides, Luehea divaricata and Araucaria angustifolia.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol	0-20
(Pereira et al., 2020)	Itapeva	February 2010	24	4320	24°04'19" S 49°04'10" W	740	Reforested Araucaria Forest 34 years	Gochnatia polymorpha, Chusquea ramossissima, other shrub and herb species, and Araucaria angustifolia.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol	0-20

(Pereira et al., 2020)		February 2010	24	4320			Native <i>Araucaria</i> Forest	<i>Dicksonia sellowiana</i> , <i>Cordyline terminalis</i> , <i>Eugenia cerasiflora</i> , <i>Allaphyllus edulis</i> , <i>Prunus myrtifolia</i> , <i>Casearia sylvestris</i> , <i>Swartzia acutifolia</i> , <i>Matayba elaeagnoides</i> , <i>Casearia decandra</i> , <i>Ocotea elegans</i> , <i>Araucaria angustifolia</i> , <i>Cedrela fissilis</i> , <i>Ocotea elegans</i> , <i>Ocotea puberula</i> and <i>Matayba elaeagnoides</i> as emergent.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol WRB/FAO (2006)	0-20
	Barra do Chapéu				24°28'40''S 49°01'07''W	785	Over 120 years			
(Pereira et al., 2020)	Iporanga	February 2010	24	4320	24°20'14''S 48°36'14''W	932	Reforested <i>Araucaria</i> Forest 36 years	<i>Araucaria angustifolia</i> and other tree and shrub species. Herbaceous and grass species occurred in places with more open vegetation.	Dystric Haplic Cambisol	0-20
(Razauskaite et al., 2020)	The north-east of Scotland	2019	12	1000-1100	57°17' N 3°73' W	NA	Young forest Less 25	juniper (<i>Juniperus co uni</i>) , <i>Calluna vulgaris</i> , <i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	podzols	0-11
(Razauskaite et al., 2020)	The north-east of Scotland	2019	12	1000-1100	57°17' N 3°73' W	NA	Reconstruction forest 25-80 years	Norway spruce (<i>Picea abies</i>) and Lodgepole pine (<i>Pinus contorta</i>)	podzols	0-11
(Razauskaite et al., 2020)	The north-east of Scotland	2019	12	1000-1100	57°17' N 3°73' W	NA	Ancient forest Over 120 years	birch (<i>Betula</i> sp.), hazel (<i>Corylus avellana</i>) and poplar (<i>Populus tremulus</i>)	podzols	0-20
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Parfenievskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°25'05"N 43°36'34"E	NA	Plantation forest 40-50 years	<i>Picea abies</i> – <i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	glacial	4-10
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Parfenievskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°25'05"N 43°36'34"E	NA	Pine and spruce 80-100 years	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> , <i>Picea abies</i> and <i>Pyrola rotundifolia</i>	glacial	4-12
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Parfenievskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°25'05"N 43°36'34"E	NA	Young forest of pine 17 years	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i> , <i>Betula pendula</i> and <i>Salix caprea</i>	glacial	0-10
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Parfenievskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°25'05"N 43°36'34"E	NA	Birch-spruce Forest 50 years	<i>Betula pendula</i> and <i>Picea abies</i>	glacial	0-10
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Parfenievskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°25'05"N 43°36'34"E	NA	Spruce forest 140-150 years	<i>Picea abies</i> and <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	glacial	0-16
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	Manturovskii, Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°21'17"N 44°41'42"E	NA	Aspen-birch plantation 40 years	<i>Populus tremula</i> , <i>Betula pendula</i> and <i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	Agrosoddy podzol	0-11

(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	<i>Manturovskii</i> , Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°21'17"N 44°41'42"E	NA	Birch-spruce Forest 100 years	<i>etula pendula–Picea abies</i>	Agrosoddy podzol	0-10
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	<i>Manturovskii</i> , Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°21'17"N 44°41'42"E	NA	Willow-birch 20 years	<i>Salix caprea, Betula pendula and Deschampsia caespitosa</i>	Agrosoddy podzol	0-10
(Ryzhova et al., 2020)	<i>Manturovskii</i> , Kostroma oblast	2019	2.1	564	58°21'17"N 44°41'42"E	NA	Birch-spruce Forest 95 years	<i>Betula pendula–Picea abies and Pyrola rotundifolia</i>	Agrosoddy podzol	0-10
(Scarciglia et al., 2020)	Calabria, southern Italy	2019	10	1257 -1634	38°30'7"-38°29'31"N 16°14'10"-16°14'42"E	1274	Undisturbed site 100 years	Over Calabrian pine	Haplic Umbrisol,	0-10
(Scarciglia et al., 2020)	Calabria, southern Italy	2019	10	1257 -1634	38°30'7"-38°29'31"N 16°14'10"-16°14'42"E	1149	reforested in Calabrian pine 59 years	Calabrian pine, Douglas-fir <i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i> (Mirb) Franco var. <i>menziesii</i>), Monterey pine (<i>Pinus radiata</i> D.Don), and some broadleaves species, Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.) and chestnut <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.	NA	0-10
(Scarciglia et al., 2020)	Calabria, southern Italy	2019	10	1257 -1634	38°30'7"-38°29'31"N 16°14'10"-16°14'42"E	1093	Turkey oak 61 years	Turkey oak, Douglas-fir <i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i> (Mirb) Franco var. <i>menziesii</i>), Monterey pine (<i>Pinus radiata</i> D.Don), and some broadleaves species, Turkey oak (<i>Quercus cerris</i> L.) and chestnut <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.	NA	0-10
(Shao et al., 2019)	the Changbai Mountain National Nature Reserve	August 2014	2.9	700	42°20'-42°24' N 127°55'-128°06' E	780–920	20 years	<i>Betula platyphylla</i> and <i>Populus davidiana</i>	alfisols	0-15
(Shao et al., 2019)	the Changbai Mountain National Nature Reserve	August 2014	2.9	700	42°20'-42°24' N 127°55'-128°06' E	780–920	80 years	<i>Acer mono</i> , <i>Fraxinus mandshurica</i> , <i>Quercus mongolica</i> , and <i>Tilia</i> <i>amurensis</i>	alfisols	0-15

(Shao et al., 2019)	the Changbai Mountain National Nature Reserve	August 2014	2.9	700	42°20'-42°24' N 127°55'-128°06' E	780-920	120 years	Acer mono, Fraxinus mandshurica, Quercus mongolica, and Tilia amurensis	alfisols	0-15
(Shao et al., 2019)	the Changbai Mountain National Nature Reserve	August 2014	2.9	700	42°20'-42°24' N 127°55'-128°06' E	780-920	200 years	Pinus koraiensis (climax species), with contributions from Acer mono, Fraxinus mandshurica, Quercus mongolica, and Tilia amurensis.	alfisols	0-15
(Shao et al., 2019)	the Changbai Mountain National Nature Reserve	August 2014	2.9	700	42°20'-42°24' N 127°55'-128°06' E	780-920	Natural forest 300 years	Pinus koraiensis (climax species), with contributions from Acer mono, Fraxinus mandshurica, Quercus mongolica, and Tilia amurensis.	alfisols	0-15
(Sheng et al., 2021)	Miyaluo Forest Reserve	July 2018	8	600-1100	31°42' -31°51' N 102° 41' -102° 4'E	3579.4-3716.7	Primary forest Over 70 years	Dominant Species is Picea, Abies	mountain brown soil series	0-10
(Sheng et al., 2021)	Miyaluo Forest Reserve	July 2018	8	600-1100	102° 41' -102° 4'E, 31°42' - 31°51' N	3551.8-3579	Coniferous broadleaved forest 35 years	Betula, Abies, Acer	brown soil series	0-10
(Sheng et al., 2021)	Miyaluo Forest Reserve	July 2018	8	600-1100	102° 41' -102° 4'E, 31°42' - 31°51' N	3435-3572.9	Broad leaved forest 35 years	Betula, Acer, Populus	brown soil series	0-10
(Shiau et al., 2020)	Lienhuachi Experimental Forest	July 2010	20.8	2200	23°54'N, 120°54'E	600 - 950	Natural broadleaf forest Over 200 years	Cryptocarya chinensis (Hance) Hemsl., Litsea acuminatae (Blume) Kurata, Prunus phaeosticta (Hance) Maxim., and Lithocarpus amygdalifolius (Skan) Hayata	Typic Dystrudept	0-10
(Shiau et al., 2020)	Lienhuachi Experimental Forest	July 2010	20.8	2200	23°54'N, 120°54'E	600 -950	Reforested coniferous forest 80 years	Calocedrus formosana (Florin) Florin, Randia cochinchinensis (Lour.) Merr, Schefflera octophylla (Lour.) Harms, and Prunus phaeosticta (Hance) Maxim	Typic Dystrudept	0-10
(Shiau et al., 2020)	Lienhuachi Experimental Forest	July 2010	20.8	2200	23°54'N, 120°54'E	600 - 950	Reforested coniferous forest 40 years	Cunninghamia lanceolate (Lamb.) Hook., Styrax formosana Matsum., and Schefflera octophylla (Lour.) Harms	Typic Dystrudept	0-10

(Singh et al., 2012)	National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow India	January 2010	18.9–32.3	900	26° 40'–45' N 80° 45'–53' E	NA	Rehabilitated Terminalia arjuna 30 years	Terminalia arjuna	NA	0-15
(Singh et al., 2012)	National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow India	January 2010	18.9–32.3	900	26° 40'–45' N 80° 45'–53' E	NA	Rehabilitated Prosopis juliflora 30 years	Prosopis juliflora	NA	0-15
(Singh et al., 2012)	National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow India	January 2010	18.9–32.3	900	26° 40'–45' N 80° 45'–53' E	NA	Rehabilitated mixed forest 50 years	About 64 species belonging to 30 families (Tripathi & Singh, 2005)	NA	0-15
(Singh et al., 2012)	Katerniaghat Wildlife Sanctuary Bahraich, India	January 2010	17–36.5	1020	28° 15' N 81° 11' E	NA	Native mixed forest Ancient	Dominance of sal (<i>Shorea robusta</i>) and teak <i>T. grandis</i> (TG) trees with understory species like <i>Terminalia alata</i> , <i>Adina cardifolia</i> , <i>Schleichera oleosa</i> , <i>Syzygium cumini</i> and <i>Mallotus philippensis</i>	NA	0-15
(Sohng et al., 2017)	Southwest Sri Lanka	2014	25–27	4000-6000	6°21' –6°27' N 80°21' –80°38'E	346–427	Caribbean pine plantations 34-38 years	Caribbean pine	ferruginous ultisols	0-10
(Sohng et al., 2017)	Southwest Sri Lanka	2014	25–27	4000-6000	6°21' –6°27' N 80°21' –80°38'E	379–673	Mature forests		ferruginous ultisols	0-10
(Sokolowska et al., 2020)	Carpathian Mountains in southern Poland	Autumn 2017	5.2	770	49°25'03N 20°23'43E	NA	succession forest 25 years	a <i>Dentario glandulosae</i> – <i>Fagetum</i> (Carpathian beech forest) vegetation complex. Carpathian beech forest	Endoskeletal Eutric Cambisols	0-10
(Sokolowska et al., 2020)	Carpathian Mountains in southern Poland	Autumn 2017	5.2	770	49°25'03N 20°23'43E	NA	old-growth forest 175 years	<i>Dentario glandulosae</i> – <i>Fagetum</i> (Carpathian beech forest) vegetation complex. Carpathian beech forest	Skeletal Eutric Cambisols	0-10
(Vasconcellos et al., 2014)	São Paulo, Brazil	January 2010	21.5	1400	22°49'42''S 46°55'34''W	650	Native trees	Myrtaceae, Rutaceae and Fabaceae Solanaceae Rubiaceae, Moraceae, Meliaceae Euphorbiaceae, Lauraceae and Mimosaceae	Acrisol FAO	0-20

(Vasconcellos et al., 2014)	São Paulo, Brazil,	January 2010	21.5	1400	22°34'38''S 47°30'27''W	605	Old recovery site 20 years	Apocynaceae Caesalpinaceae Flacourtiaceae Malvaceae Rutaceae	Ferralsol	0-20
(Vasconcellos et al., 2014)	São Paulo, Brazil,	January 2010	21.5	1400	22°49'06''S 47°24'52''W	540	Recovery site 10 years	Verbanaceae Meliaceae, Lauraceae and Caricaceae Boraginaceae	Lixisol	0-20
(Velooso et al., 2018)	Rio Negrinho Santa Catarina, Brazil	December 2012	15.5–17.0	1360–1670	26°23'11'' - 26°23'19''S, 49°33'34'' -49°34'12''W	900	Natural forest Over 42 years	<i>Cyathea</i> spp., <i>Myrcia splendens</i> , <i>Dicksonia sellowiana</i> , <i>Myrsine umbellata</i> , <i>Nectandra megapotamica</i> , <i>Prunus myrtifolia</i> , <i>Pimenta pseudocaryophyllus</i> , <i>Araucaria angustifolia</i> , <i>Ocotea porosa</i> , and <i>Drimys brasiliensis</i>	Cambisol	0-5
(Velooso et al., 2018)	Rio Negrinho Santa Catarina, Brazil	December 2012	15.5–17.0	1360–1670	26°23'11'' - 26°23'19''S, 49°33'34'' -49°34'12''W	900	loblolly pine plantations 17 years	loblolly pine (<i>Pinus taeda</i> L.)	Cambisol	0-5
(Velooso et al., 2018)	Rio Negrinho Santa Catarina, Brazil	December 2012	15.5–17.0	1360–1670	26°23'11'' - 26°23'19''S, 49°33'34'' -49°34'12''W	900	loblolly pine plantations 32 years	loblolly pine (<i>Pinus taeda</i> L.)	Cambisol	0-5
(Vogel & Conedera, 2020)	Lago Maggiore, southern Swiss Alps	2019	11	2 000	46°12'23''N 8°40'29''E	450-865	natural forested	European chestnut (<i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.), oak (<i>Quercus spec. L.</i>), alder (<i>Alnus glutinosa</i> (L.) Gaertn), and lime (<i>Tilia cordata</i> Mill.)	NA	0-10
(Vogel & Conedera, 2020)	Lago Maggiore, southern Swiss Alps	2019	11	2 000	46°12'23''N 8°40'29''E	470 - 780	Reforested abandoned terraces 36-46 years	European chestnut, hazel (<i>Corylus avellana</i> L.), oak and lime	NA	0-10
(Wan et al., 2019)	Xiaolongshan Nature Reserve	September 2017	7–12	600-900	34°16'-35°25' N 106°15'-106°30'E	1663-1760	unmanaged forest over 40 years	<i>Q. aliena</i> , alongside, <i>Quercus liaotungensis</i> Koidz, <i>Pinus armandii</i> Franch, and <i>Carya cathayensis</i> Sarg.	yellow cinnamon soil	0-20
(Wan et al., 2019)	Xiaolongshan Nature Reserve	September 2017	7–12	600-900	34°16'-35°25' N 106°15'-106°30'E	1699-1749	Close-to-nature forest management 5 years	<i>Quercus aliena</i> var. <i>acuteserrata</i> , <i>Quercus wutaishansea</i> Mary, and <i>Pinus tabuliformis</i>	yellow cinnamon soil	0-20

(Wan et al., 2019)	Xiaolongshan Nature Reserve	September 2017	7–12	600-900	34°16'-35°25' N 106°15'–106°30'E	1664-1727	Structure-based Forest management 5years	<i>Q. aliena</i> , alongside, <i>Quercus liaotungensis</i> Koidz, <i>Pinus armandii</i> Franch, and <i>Carya cathayensis</i> Sarg.	yellow cinnamon soil	0-20
(Wan et al., 2019)	Xiaolongshan Nature Reserve	September 2017	7–12	600-900	34°16'-35°25' N 106°15'–106°30'E	1683-1711	Secondary forest comprehensive silviculture 5years	<i>Q. aliena</i> , alongside, <i>Quercus liaotungensis</i> Koidz, <i>Pinus armandii</i> Franch, and <i>Carya cathayensis</i> Sarg.	yellow cinnamon soil	0-20
(Xiao et al., 2020)	Pingjiang Basin, Jiangxi Province, China	December 2019	18.9	1538	115°16'07"E 26°19' 20"N	127 -1207	Artificial forest 14 years	<i>Pinus massoniana</i> Lamb. <i>Lespedeza bicolor</i> Turcz and <i>Camellia oleifera</i> Abel	Quaternary red soil	0-10
(Xiao et al., 2020)	Pingjiang Basin, Jiangxi Province, china	December 2019	18.9	1538	115°16'06"E 26°20' 54"N	127 -1207	Artificial forest 24 years	<i>Pinus massoniana</i> Lamb. <i>Lespedeza bicolor</i> Turcz and <i>Camellia oleifera</i> Abel	Quaternary red soil	0-10
(Xiao et al., 2020)	Pingjiang Basin, Jiangxi Province, China	December 2019	18.9	1538	115°16'07"E 26°19' 20"N	127 -1207	Artificial forest 34 years	<i>Pinus massoniana</i> Lamb. <i>Lespedeza bicolor</i> Turcz and <i>Camellia oleifera</i> Abel	Quaternary red soil	0-10
(Xiao et al., 2020)	Pingjiang Basin, Jiangxi Province, China	December 2019	18.9	1538	115°14'58"E 26°13' 36"N	127 -1207	Undisturbed old-growth forest	<i>Castanopsis carlesii</i> (Hemsl.) Hay., <i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i> (Lamb.) Hook., <i>Cyclobalanopsis glauca</i> (Thunberg) Oerste	Quaternary red soil	0-10
(Xiong et al., 2020)	Guangdong Province, China	October 2015	21.7 -23	1400-1956	NA	NA	Old-growth Forest over 400 years	<i>Aporosa yunnanensis</i> , <i>Schima superba</i> , <i>Blastus cochinchinensis</i> , <i>Castanopsis chinensis</i> , and <i>Cryptocarya chinensis</i>	Ultisol and Oxisol	0-10
(Xiong et al., 2020)	Guangdong Province, China	October 2015	21.7 -23	1400-1956	NA	NA	The forest planted with native species 51 years	<i>Carallia brachiata</i> , <i>Acacia confusa</i> , <i>Syzygium rehderianum</i> , <i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> , and <i>Ficus chlorocarpa</i>	Ultisol and Oxisol	0-10

(Xiong et al., 2020)	Guangdong Province, China	October 2015	21.7 -23	1400-1956	NA	NA	The forest planted with native species 31 years	<i>Schima superba</i> , <i>Castanopsis hystrix</i> , <i>Schima wallichii</i> , and <i>Michelia macclurei</i>	Ultisol and Oxisol	0-10
(Xiong et al., 2020)	Guangdong Province, China	October 2015	21.7 -23	1400-1956	NA	NA	Plantation <i>Acacia mangium</i> 31 years	<i>Acacia mangium</i>	Ultisol and Oxisol	0-10
(Xiong et al., 2020)	Guangdong Province, China	October 2015	21.7 -23	1400-1956	NA	NA	The forest was planted with coniferous species. 31 years	<i>Pinus massoniana</i> , <i>Pinus elliotii</i> , and <i>Cunninghamia lanceolata</i>	Ultisol and Oxisol	0-10
(Yao et al., 2019)	Changting County, Fujian Province, China	July 2018	19	1621	25°33'-25°48'N 116°18'-116°31'E	NA	Native forest Over 40 years	<i>Pinus massoniana</i> and <i>Schima superba</i>	Ultisols	0-20
(Yao et al., 2019)	Changting County, Fujian Province, China	July 2018	19	1621	25°33'-25°48'N 116°18'-116°31'E	NA	Reforestation 8 years	<i>P. massoniana</i>	Ultisols	0-20
(Yao et al., 2019)	Changting County, Fujian Province, China	July 2018	19	1621	25°33'-25°48'N 116°18'-116°31'E	NA	Reforestation 36 years	<i>P. massoniana</i>	Ultisols	0-20
(Yesilonis et al., 2016)	Rhode River estuary, Maryland	2015	13	1146	38°53' N 75°33' W	NA	Reforestations 50-70 years	<i>Liriodendron tulipifera</i> , <i>Liquidambar styraciflua</i> , <i>Acer rubrum</i> , <i>Prunus serotina</i> and <i>Acer negundo</i> .	Annapolis and Donlonton	0-10
(Yesilonis et al., 2016)	Rhode River estuary, Maryland	2015	13	1146	38°53' N 75°33' W	NA	Reforestations 120-150 years	several species of oaks, (<i>Quercus</i> spp.), American beech (<i>Fagus grandifolia</i>), and hickories (<i>Carya</i> spp.)	Adelphia, Holmdel, Annapolis and Collington	0-10
(Yesilonis et al., 2016)	Rhode River estuary, Maryland	2015	13	1146	38°53' N 75°33' W	NA	Natural forest Over 200 years	several species of oak (<i>Quercus</i>) with the dominant species being chestnut oak (<i>Q. prinus</i>)	Collington, Annapolis Wist, and Donlonton	0-10

(Yu et al.)	Heshan National Field Research Station	July 2019	21.7	1,700	22°34' N, 112°50' E	NA	monoculture 35 years	Acacia mangium	NA	0-20
(Yu et al.)	Heshan National Field Research Station	July 2019	21.7	1,700	22°34' N 112°50' E	NA	mixed Eucalyptus plantation 35 years	Eucalyptus exserta, Eucalyptus citriodora, and Eucalyptus camaldulensis	NA	0-20
(Yu et al.)	Heshan National Field Research Station	July 2019	21.7	1,700	22°34' N 112°50' E	NA	a mixed plantation of coniferous 35 years	Cunninghamia lanceolata and Pinus massoniana	NA	0-20
(Yu et al.)	Heshan National Field Research Station	July 2019	21.7	1,700	22°34' N 112°50' E	NA	Native species forest 35 years	Schima superba and Schima wallichii	NA	0-20
(Zhang et al., 2019)	Xiaoliang Tropical Coastal Ecosystem Research Station	May 2016	23	1400–1700	110°54'18"E, 21°27'49"N	NA	Nearly undisturbed forest Over 200 years	Sterculia lanceolate, Psychotria rubra, Memecylon ligustrifolium, Uvaria microcarpa	NA	0-10
(Zhang et al., 2019)	Xiaoliang Tropical Coastal Ecosystem Research Station	May 2016	23	1400–1700	110°54'18"E, 21°27'49"N	NA	Restored secondary forest 56 years	Syzygium levinei, Cinnamomum camphora, Carallia brachiata, Psychotria rubra, Memecylon ligustrifolium, Syzygium bullockii, Chukrasia tabularis, Litsca glutinosa, Diplospora dubia	NA	0-10
(Zhang et al., 2019)	Xiaoliang Tropical Coastal Ecosystem Research Station	May 2016	23	1400–1700	110°54'18"E, 21°27'49"N	NA	Managed Eucalyptus plantation 55 years	Eriachne pallescens	NA	0-10
(Zhong et al., 2018)	Lianjiabian Forest Farm	September 2015	10	587	36°02' N, 108°32' E	1450	Pioneer forest Around 110 years	Populus davidiana	alcareous cinnamon soil (Ustalfs)	0–20
(Zhong et al., 2018)	Lianjiabian Forest Farm	September 2015	10	587	36°02' N, 108°31' E	1449	Natural forest Over 160 years	Quercus liaotungensis	alcareous cinnamon soil (Ustalfs)	0–20
(Zinn et al., 2014)	Minas Gerais, Brazil	2013	19.4	1530	21°13'42"S, 43°17'09"W	891	Native forest	Semi-deciduous forest	Lavras Oxisol,	0-12

(Zinn et al., 2014)	Minas Gerais, Brazil	2013	19.4	1530	21°13'42"S, 43°17'09"W	891	Pinus stands 20 years	Pinus tecunumanni	Lavras Oxisol,	0-10
(Zinn et al., 2014)	Itabira, Brazil	2013	21.1	1491	19°35'47"S, 43°17'09" W	970	Native forest	Semi-deciduous forest	Itabira Ultisol	0-9
(Zinn et al., 2014)	Itabira, Brazil	2013	21.1	1491	19°35'47"S, 43°17'09" W	970	Pinus stands 20 years	Pinus tecunumanni	Itabira Ultisol	0-10

MAT means the mean annual temperature and MAP means the mean annual precipitation

Appendix 1: List of the 60 primary articles from which the data were extracted for this study

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Appendix 2 Funnel Plot for topsoil properties

Funnel Plot

A SOC

Funnel Plot

B bulk density

Funnel Plot

C soil C/N ratio

Funnel Plot

D pH value

